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Intercultural Communication and Church Leadership Administration in Lagos Pluralistic Society, Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Pluralism is a state in which people of different cultural backgrounds, socio-economic status, religions, races, ideology, philosophy, etc., are together in a society, but continue to exhibit their different traditions and interests. The existence of diverse cultural and religious belief systems in the metropolis of Lagos with virtually all the major 380 ethnic groups in Nigeria and the naturalized Portuguese, Sierra Leoneans, Liberians, Kenyans, Lebanese, Arabs and Chard business tycoons coupled with the effects of modernity and globalization have made Lagos Churches pluralistic causing constant change in co-existence and intercultural relationship with its antecedent challenges of suspicion, prejudice, disunity, tribalism and poor integration in spite of the rich array of culture and civilization. Scholars have carried out some research on Church leadership roles in managing the recurrent problems. However, intercultural communication skills for Leadership Administration in Lagos has not been given adequate attention, this lacuna is the crux of this paper. The paper employed historical and quantitative methods premised on Xiuwen and Razali's Intercultural Communication Skill theoretical framework, which states that, in human society, communication provides a premise to share pluralistic worldview, ideas, moral values, emotional intelligent and feelings, promoting mutual relationship in the society. The finding reveals that, the churches in Lagos are characterized with multi-cultural diversity because of the variegated interconnectedness, which makes it increasingly clear that Church Leadership requires intercultural communication skills for understanding individuality and corresponding cultural traits for encouraging oneness and unity in the churches. Conclusively, Intercultural Communication skill is a veritable mechanism for church leaders in managing and administering their pluralistic congregations for cohesion and integration in spite of the cultural diversities. It is recommended therefore that, the multicultural composition of the churches in Lagos should make the adoption of intercultural communication a crucial skill for church leadership administration.

Keywords: Intercultural Communication, Church Leadership Administration, Lagos Pluralistic Society, Cultural Diversity, Lagos State.

Introduction

Since its advent in Jerusalem, the Church has always been a composition of people from different cultural and ethnic nationalities. For instance, the early church was home to people from different languages, cultural affiliations and ethnic nationalities. In other words, like any human institution or organization, the church is also characterized with cultural and language diversity. Apostle Paul in Romans 11: 13-25 also remarks about the uneasiness between the original and wild olives – representing the Jews and the Gentiles in the Roman Church. The existence of diverse cultural and religious belief systems in the metropolis of Lagos with virtually all the major 380 ethnic groups and over 500 languages in Nigeria (Atowoju, 2024). This array of culture and civilization which resulted from the various ethnic diversities has brought a lot of beauty and splendor to the socio-economic, religious and political life of Lagos and the Christian community in particular as one of the microcosms of Lagos religious communities. In spite of the rich array of culture and civilization, the multicultural diversity and constant change in co-existence and intercultural relationship has equally come with its antecedent challenges of disunity, tribalism and poor integration. Scholars have carried out some research on Church leadership roles in managing the recurrent problems. However, intercultural communication skills for Leadership Administration among Christians in Lagos have not been given adequate attention, this lacuna is the crux of this paper.

Lagos Pluralism and Cultural Diversity

Lagos also known as Eko (as its traditional Yoruba name) is primarily a Yoruba socio-cultural setting, Yoruba people are the major ethnic group, but the population does not exclude other ethnic groups in Nigeria, these include but not limited to Edo, Hausa, Igbo, Fulani, Efik, Igarra and several individuals from other countries, Britons, Kenyans, Sierra Leoneans, Portuguese, Liberians, Senegalese, Malians, Togolese, Arabs, Nigeriens, Beninese, Ghanaians, Chadians, Cameroonians, Lebanese, Brazilians, etc. (Patrick 2014). This makes Lagos the most populated and culturally diversified city in Nigeria. Lagos is evidently a centre of diverse cultural and ethnic nationalities (Lagos State Government, 2021). The peculiarity of cultural diversity in Lagos is hinged on strong attraction to Lagos' beautiful landscapes, infrastructures, job opportunities, industrial and economic development, urbanisation, globalisation and civility of Lagosians to people from other parts of Nigeria and the world at large (Lagos, 2021). These attractions are also based on strong economy, commerce and industry, and socio-political inclusiveness. Etomes (2020) stresses that Lagos metropolis gives the platform for openness, innovation and increase investment for people from different part of the world.

Lagos is widely recognised as the commercial centre and epicentre of all ethnic nationalities in Nigeria and other nations around the world. Lagos inclusiveness encompasses both indigenes and non-indigenes in the state. Non-indigenes have become a fundamental factor in Lagos state politics, religion, economy, social and leadership administration in all spheres of life. No state in Nigeria has such cultural accommodation, tolerance and open playing field for leadership aspiration either in civil service or political office. For instance, non-indigenes of Lagos dominate the market and business life of the state, which in turn contributes enormously to the economic development of Lagos. Most of the industries and private organisations are established by non-indigenes of Lagos state. For instance, the Dangote Refinery owned by Aliko Dangote was inaugurated on the 22nd of May, 2023 in Lekki, Lagos,

Nigeria. When in full operation, it is expected to have the capacity to process about 650,000 barrels of crude oil per day, making it the largest single-train refinery in the world. According Desmond (2023), the investment worth of over 19 billion US dollars.

The role of communication in any organization cannot be over-emphasized as it has been termed by many as the life-support or blood needed for survival. In a pluralistic society of Lagos, intercultural- communication ensures that there is a proper interaction between persons at different levels of an organization. Xiuwen and Razali's (2020) state that, in human society, communication provides a premise to share pluralistic worldview, ideas, moral values, emotional intelligent and feelings, promoting mutual relationship in the society. Intercultural communication or communication between people of different cultural backgrounds has always been and will probably remain an important precondition of human co-existence on earth.

The Concept of Communication

There is no universal accepted definition of communication among scholars. This makes the subject of communication a very difficult to define in a particular way, because it involves series of different conducts associating to the transmission of information among people (Jiequ and Zhu et al, 2020). Experience also shows that communication means to share or to be in relation with (Cherrez-Ojeda, et al 2020). For instance, communication is an apparent answer to the painful divisions between a person and other, private and public, and inner thought and outer world (Culmin, et al 2021). In this sense, communication plays important roles in peaceful co-existence between individuals and general society. Imagine if there is no medium of communication among the people, how would the world and creations survive? In actual fact, communication is key to existence, it gives life and meaning to human existence. Communication is conceptualized in different ways by many individuals. It can be viewed as the process of transferring information and meaning from a sender to a receiver with the use of a medium in which the communicated information is understood by both the sender and the receiver. Communication is a process that allows human beings to exchange information by several methods. In its simplest form, communication is the use of words to describe and convey a message or give information to another person. We communicate using language as a code to share information, ideas and feelings.

Concept of Intercultural Communication

According to Oana-Antonia (2019), intercultural Communication is regarded as ability and skill needed in interaction with people from different cultures. Therefore, communication is not as easy as many people think it is, especially, when communicating with people from different cultural background. Effective communication demands skills and understanding of different cultures and languages. It is not cultures that communicate, whatever that might imply, but people with different cultural backgrounds that do. In general, the term cross-cultural is probably best used for comparisons between cultures. Bearing in mind that every religious set up is a mixture of people from different cultural backgrounds, which brings about complexity and plurality (Mayda, 2022). It is noteworthy that intercultural communication is studied widely across various academic disciplines due to international relation.

The world today has become a global village whereby communication with people different from one's cultural orientation is daily experience in every institution of live such as the

church, private cooperate organization and government public establishment. For Byram & Golubeva, (2020), the concept of intercultural communication can be regarded as communication among individuals from different cultural and ethnic nationalities in this age of globalization. This means for a successful interaction among people from different cultural affiliation, the knowledge of intercultural communication is a perquisite (Sinden, 2021) Relating this concept of intercultural communication to the church context which is the focus of this study, the church is like epicentre for different means cultural background. Therefore, intercultural communication becomes an essential tool for effective information dissemination among people of diverse cultural orientations. The skill of intercultural communication is beyond creating of awareness or passing of information among people from different cultural understanding, but also crucial for leadership in a multicultural context. The working environment in the whole world is all encompassing in terms of gender base, religious and cultural divide. Effective leadership in a multicultural location requires knowledge of intercultural communication. For example, leadership is service. In order to render effective service delivery in the church context or any human institution on the surface of the earth, intercultural communication knowledge and skill is inevitable.

Conceptual Understanding of the Church

Berg (2020) narratives about the early church reveals the dynamic nature of the Christian communities (Acts 1: 1-6). The Church is rooted in the heart of God's mission and Gospel of Jesus. The Church lies at the very centre of the eternal purpose of God on earth from generation to generation. Pillay (2020) argues that the church is the gathering of the people called out of the world for Jesus' own glory (1 Peter 2:9). Therefore, the mission of Jesus was concerned with the creation of community, which formed the basis of the Church that was inaugurated on the day of Pentecost.

Understanding Difference Between Cultures and Communication Patterns

The term culture refers to all the characteristics common to a particular group of people that are learned and not given by nature. Hunt & D'Érrico (2000) emphasised that the members of a group have two legs is not a cultural characteristic but a natural one, while a special but common way of walking would probably be cultural. Culture is complex phenomenon which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by a person as a member of society (Staff, 2020). In relation to this, culture constitutes everything that controls life and society values and cosmology. Kaplan (2018) highlighted the following cultural patterns or norms that govern the behaviour of a group of people, according to their traditions, customs, habits, beliefs, geographical location and experience in establishing models of behaviour.

- i. **Patterns of behaviour:** common ways of behaving, from ways of speaking to ways of conducting commerce and industry, where the behaviour can be intentional or unintentional, aware or unaware or individual or interactive.
- ii. **Patterns of artefacts:** common ways of manufacturing and using material things, from pens to houses where artefacts include dwellings, tools, machines or media. The art factual dimension of culture is usually given special attention in museums.

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- iii. **Imprints in nature:** the long-lasting imprints left by a group in the natural surroundings where such imprints include agriculture, trash, roads or intact or ruined human habitations.
 - iv. **Patterns of thought:** common ways of thinking, where thinking includes factual beliefs, values, norms, and emotional attitudes (Neff & Mathew, 2020).

Communication is very important wherever people find themselves. Nevertheless, communication across cultures can be very difficult because cultures have ways of communicating both formal and informal. Cultures have one thing in common, which is that they can get offended if you do not understand their communication practices. If that has to be avoided in Intercultural Communication, people have to learn how to communicate. In his view, Hadad (2021), describes language as an effective instrument for intercultural communication. This is because it is tied to cultural pattern in every locality or society. Hence, beyond traditional writing of language, greater consideration must be given to the conditions for understanding in order to appropriately relate with people from other cultural settings.

Models and Approaches to Intercultural Communication

1. Social science approach: This model focuses on observing the behaviour of a person from a different culture in order to describe it and compare it with other cultures (Ndhlóvu, 2022). It also examines the ways in which individuals adjust their communication with others in different situations, depending on who they are talking to. For example, we would tell the same story differently to our best friend than we would to our grandmother or an elderly member of the society.
2. Interpretive approach: This theory focuses on accumulating knowledge about a culture through communication in the form of shared stories based on subjective individual experiences (Allard-Kropp, 2020). The main focus is on intercultural communication as it is used in particular speech in different communities, so ethnography plays a major role here. Because the individual context is so important for this model, it does not strive to make generalized predictions based on its findings.
3. Dialectical approach: This method examines aspects of intercultural communication in the form of six dichotomies, namely cultural-individual, personal-contextual, difference-similarities, static-dynamic, history/past-present/future, and privilege-disadvantage (Heggernes, 2021). A dialectical approach helps us think about culture and intercultural communication in complex ways, so we can avoid categorizing everything in either-or dichotomies by adopting a broader approach and acknowledging the tensions that must be negotiated.
4. Critical approach: This approach examines cultures according to their differences compared to the researcher's own culture and, in particular, how these cultures are portrayed in the media (Sharifovna, 2021) The critical approach is complex and multifaceted and therefore leads to a rich understanding of intercultural communication.

Church Leadership Management and Administration in Lagos Pluralistic Society

According to United Nation Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, cultural diversity is a common heritage of humanity (Ridley, et al). Lagos is a pluralistic society and

most of the churches in Lagos are unarguably multi-ethnic and multi-linguistic. Cultural diversity is synonymous to multiculturalism which promotes congregational groupings of people with different cultural backgrounds (Park, 2022). In this sense, cultural diversity covers values, beliefs, attitudes, language, customs, and behaviours. Likewise, Karjalainen (2020) cultural diversity is personified in the distinctiveness and variety of identities among groups in the society. The distinctiveness of human Cultural heritage is rooted in race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, gender, and several differences related to human existence. Cultural diversity exposes people to different cultural orientations and norms different from one's culture. Therefore, leadership management and administration in the pluralistic society like Lagos requires a deep understanding of intercultural communication. Leadership can be defined as the process of getting things done through and with people. This definition is apt because three variables are involved in this process. The activity to be done, the people to do the activity, and the person to get them perform the task or activity. This can be likened to management of people and resources to achieve a particular goal. Definitely, management has three dimensions which are management of people, management of work and management of operation (Tyari, 2023) In other words, there is overlapping function between leadership and management. In explicit way, Mohta (2022) describes management as the integral process of planning, organizing, staffing, direction, controlling and coordinating all activities in as established organisations. In another way, Herry (2023) conceptualised management as coordination and administration of operation to achieve organizational desired goals per time. Furthermore, some scholars conceptualized management as the act of bringing people together to attain stated aims and objectives efficiently and effectively through available resources (Kaehler and Grundei, 2019).

However, beyond managing of physical resources, church management encompasses managing the spiritual life and growth of members. Church leadership management is also conceived as ministry, stewardship and managing of God's resources (Boaheng, 2021). From business orientation, Kwabena, et al (2021) conceived church management as business function that provides leadership support to organizations' resources to achieve vision and planned goals of the organisation. These scholars argued that, though the church is not a business organisation, but management of church members and resources required provision of leadership and management structure. In Church management leaders are not passive persons, but they are also workers because they have to initiate the activities to be done and also see to it that they are done well. In actual fact, the multicultural combination of the church demands development of management skills in pastoral training that can adequately manage inter-relational activities within the multicultural milieu (Chatira and Mwenje, 2018).

The Conversational Constraint Theory

The theory focuses mode of conversation that individual exhibits at one time or the other. This theory tries to investigate how and why people choose to communicate in a certain manner. Conversational constraint theory provides some common conversational constraint which are clarity, minimizing imposition, consideration for other's feelings, risking negative evaluation by the hearer; and effectiveness (Min-Sun,1994) However, people respond to some of these constraints in different ways. The reason is that there is

individual difference, and several factors such as family background and up bring, environment and cultural orientation contribute to it.

The church is the body of Christ and community of believers from diverse cultural backgrounds and ethnic nationalities. It is expected that the church should manifest the love of Christ, and live in peace and harmony with one another. The church should be a healthy and loving community regardless of cultural or ethnic background of members. This will only possible if the leaders and members care about others and careful about their manner of communication. Some of the indicators highlighted by this theory are so crucial for healthy church management. Management of people demands effective communication. Hence, effective communication requires clarity, and consideration for other's feelings.

Ruben's Behavioural Theory of Intercultural Competence

This theory explored behavioural approach to examining the gap between knowing and doing, that is, between what people knows to be intercultural competence and what they do in intercultural situations (Sinicrope, et al, 2007). The theory constitutes several dimensions that are essential in determining and measuring individual intercultural communicative competence. These dimensions are display of respect, interaction posture, orientation to knowledge, empathy, self-oriented role behaviour, interaction management, and tolerance for ambiguity. The leaders and church members are expected to manifest Christ like character, respect for people regardless of their cultural affiliation, showing empathy for others and tolerate every member in the congregation no matter social class, sexual orientation and level of service in the church.

Conclusion

The paper reveals that attitude and perception of some leaders towards people from different languages and cultures usually caused conflict in the church. Essentially, wrong attitude and negative perception about people from different language and culture always result to superiority complex and undue segregation in the church. The reality of cultural diversity, uniqueness and importance of every culture should not be neglected or ignored in the church for efficient pastoral ministry, leadership administration and effective service delivery to the congregation without cultural or language discrimination and disparity. This is in tandem with the view of Xiuwen and Razali's concept of intercultural communication skill, which states that, in human society, communication provides a premise to share pluralistic worldview, ideas, moral values, emotional intelligent and feelings, promoting mutual relationship in the society. Intercultural communication or communication between people of different cultural backgrounds has always been and will probably remain an important precondition of human co-existence on earth.

In providing good leadership in the church, the leaders should apply their intercultural communication skills and abilities such as beliefs, values, ethics, character and knowledge as well as selfless service to the Church. Church management is combining the spiritual and the organizational work. In this wise, the Church is both the body of Christ and a human institution. Whilst there are Biblical standards and terms or definitions, Philosophies of management are also embedded into Christian Organizations like Churches, and ministries. Most importantly, the purpose of management in Churches is to create a peaceful environment for spiritual service, a sense of shared mission, stewardship of resources and mutual supportiveness.

Recommendations

The purpose of a Christian ministry is not excellent management per se but a means of serving God. Leadership, management and administration of the Church is to be people oriented and participative. The leadership places high value on cooperation and teamwork. Team members are motivated by a shared sense of vision and mission which is more important to them than personal gain. Goals are pursued selflessly and sacrificially. A key concept of leadership, management and administration is to help the team members become more Christ like. Management in Churches is ultimately a partnership with God built on prayer, faith and obedience.

The Bible unveils that right from the period of early church that the first set of Jesus' disciples presided over, identity discrimination was a major conflict. The writer of the Acts of the Apostles explicitly narrated the bias of Hebraic Jews against Hellenistic Jews. In those days when the numbers of disciples were increasing, the Hellenistic Jews among them complained against the Hebraic Jews because their widows were being overlooked in the daily distribution of food. In contemporary time, experiences also show that self-worth and face service are parts of the reasons for several conflict in the church. Identity or Face Negotiation theory deals with people's reaction and identity management during intercultural engagement.

The leadership and member of the church should be able to understand, accept and tolerate the culture of every other people group for the purpose of accommodating one another and fulfilling the purpose of existence of the church. In actual fact, multi-ethnic reality of the church is a basis for the relevance of communication adaptation theory. Experience shows that no church is mono cultural or ethnic. Unfortunately, the contemporary church is characterized with difference social status, disparity, ethnic and cultural discrimination. Members are seen themselves as member of the same cultural background instead of one body of Christ. Accommodation theory sets antidote to ethnocentric and all forms of attitude that are contrary to what the church represents without losing one's original identity and cultural value. This theory is equally relevant in promoting unity, fellowship and mutual love among members of the Church.

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